

EXPRESSION OF NOUNS AND VERBS IN THE SPEECH OF UZBEKI CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12741746>

Annotation. In this article, the speech of 10 preschool children aged 4-6 years was studied. In this process, several qualities of children's speech, such as the ratio of nouns and verbs, sentence length, sentence structure, and speech speed, were studied. Spontaneous speech of adults between 20-40 years of age was also analyzed in order to compare with children.

Key words: speed of speech, spontaneous speech, noun lexeme, verb lexeme, auxiliary verbs.

Introduction. In the fields of world linguistics, psychology, psycholinguistics, many speech situations such as children's word acquisition, speech development, and second language acquisition have been studied, and all of these are directly related to the child's social environment. In the following few small studies, we can see the analysis of children's spontaneous speech. In the article written by T. Twilla, Sh. Marilyn, N. Letitia, naturalistic examples of adult and children's speech are considered. In the study, the question of the extent to which nouns and verbs are used in children's speech, which word group is used more in the communication process, and the results showed that emerging speech data, English and Italian speaking children produce more nouns than verbs in their early vocabulary. issue, but Mandarin's results are different. Mandarin-speaking children used more verbs than nouns.

A collaborative study by Sabine Stoll, Baltasar Bikel, Elene Il Evan, and Netra P. Paudyol (2012) examines noun-verb ratio in the speech of Chingtang children under 4 years of age. The mothers of the children selected for the study worked in the fields, and the children were raised by grandmothers and nannies. The children had at least three siblings. Children's speech was recorded for 4 hours for 18 months by installing a camera and microphone in the place where children play. In this case, children interacted with other children or adults. Each child's speech was compared with that of an adult. A table of nouns and verbs used in children's speech has been compiled. According to the results of the experiment, the use of nouns in children's speech was much higher than that of verbs. It is noted that Chingtang verb morphology is quite complex. It was also mentioned that this factor affects the system of using the verb. The speech was recorded for 4 hours for 18 months. In this case, children interacted with other children or adults. Each child's speech was compared with that of an adult. A table of nouns and verbs used in children's speech has been compiled. According to the results of the experiment, the use of nouns in children's speech was much higher than that of verbs. It is noted that Chingtang verb morphology is quite complex.

In 2010, A. Hopurchuoglu studied the speech of 5-6-year-old Turkish children in his dissertation entitled "Study of the use of verbs in terms of language development of Turkish

children attending preschool educational institutions". According to the socio-economic background of the children, he divided them into 3 groups, that is, high, middle, and low. Conducted research in 3 stages. In the 1st stage, 3 stories were told and pictures were shown and children were asked to retell the story. In the 2nd stage, questions are asked from certain topics. In phase 3, they played the game in groups and their conversations during the game were recorded. As a result of the research, children belonging to high socio-political groups can use language units better than children from middle and lower groups. Relatively many usages of verbs have also been observed. A good socio-economic status of the family contributes positively to the child's language development. Parents with higher socioeconomic status can provide more opportunities for their children.

In a study conducted by English scholars Nicholas A. Lester, Balthasar Bickel, Stephen Moran, and Sabine Stoll, a study was conducted to examine the relationship between prosody and syntactic speech in the speech of young children and adults. The conclusion that the duration of nouns is longer than that of verbs, it has been verified that in Chintang, which is a morphologically rich language, the noun *a* is distinguished by the duration of verbs. In the second part, a study was conducted to determine the ratio of nouns and verbs in the speech speed of adults and children. During the study, voice recordings of adults and children were collected and presented in a general statistical table, in which the number of lexemes with nouns, verbs and lexemes with verbs was determined. 6 children and 155 adults around children took part in this process, totaling 987,672 words of speech produced by children and speech around children. The records were recorded in a natural environment without the intervention of researchers. Then the rate of speech was calculated, which was calculated as the number of segments divided by the length of words in seconds. Similarly, the natural speech of adults was analyzed. Their voice recordings were recorded during exposures. Prosodic differences between nouns and verbs were observed after the speech rate was calculated, and the overall results were tabulated in Table 1. The age of the speakers was very important.

It should be said that Uzbek linguists have not done enough research on this topic, and there are no articles on the expression of word groups in children's speech and which word groups they use most in their speech. Western scientists have shared their knowledge on this topic in their research. Based on co-authorship, we monitored the extent to which word groups are used in Uzbek children's speech. We have conducted a number of experiments on the way to our goal. We observed the speech of children of kindergarten age (4-6 years old). The purpose of this was to study the use of nouns and verbs in children's speech and to determine their speech speed. Within the framework of the research topic, we thoroughly studied the researches and a number of articles of foreign scientists. In particular, we used articles written by English and Turkish scientists.

Method. 5 boys and 5 girls aged 4-5-6 were taken for the experiment. For the purpose of comparison with children, 6 men and 4 women between the ages of 20-40 were taken. We have prepared questions on various topics to check spontaneous speech. Taking into account that there should be at least 200 words to check spontaneous speech, we recorded the children's speech by showing them colored pictures and asking them to tell the events depicted in them. Since young children cannot freely communicate with strangers, we recorded them in the form of a voice message through their relatives and adults through the Telegram social network. We converted the sounds into text.

Result.
Table 1.

Children											
No	Partici pants	noun	A lexeme with a noun	Ve rb	Verb lexem e	Auxiliar y verbs	Conjug ated verbs	Se nt en ce	Unfinished sentences (%)	Sente nce lengt h	Spe ech rate
1	A1	84	69	39	20	7	24	49	4	8.1	31.5
2	A2	116	77	40	23	2	21	50	2	6.2	31.6
3	A3	78	56	24	20	6	17	55	1.81	7.5	35.6
4	A4	63	39	30	12	2	15	63	33.3	6	29.1
5	A5	90	44	28	16	1	7	53	32.07	5	30.2
6	A6	80	60	32	25	1	30	64	17.1	7	33.8
7	A7	72	59	34	28	5	28	69	2.8	4	29.7
8	A8	75	65	35	26	5	33	56	5.3	5.7	26.4
9	A9	67	56	40	30	2	28	62	8.06	6.3	28.4
10	A10	70	66	37	25	4	35	59	6.8	5.7	30.3
Average value		79.5	59.1	33.9	22.5	3.5	23.8	58	11.3	6.15	27.82

Table 2.

Adult participants											
No	Participa nts	no un	A lexeme with a noun	Ve rb	Verb lexem e	Auxiliar y verbs	Conjug ated verbs	Se nt en ce	Unfinished sentences (%)	Sente nce lengt h	Spe ech rate
1	B1	62	48	46	30	5	30	25	7.6	14.9	65.3

2	B2	41	56	39	28	4	35	23	0	19.3	50
3	B3	75	53	36	23	2	28	36	0	10.6	64.3
4	B4	62	47	41	33	4	10	37	21	10	50.5
5	B5	83	32	38	25	3	12	30	3.3	13	38
6	B6	64	38	39	29	5	25	21	0	12.4	47.3
7	B7	70	45	40	28	8	33	15	13.3	10.8	55.5
8	B8	72	55	44	29	2	34	27	14.8	11	45.3
9	B9	67	50	48	30	3	35	23	0	15	62.6
10	B10	77	40	38	27	6	27	32	0	14.3	56.3
Average value		67.3	46.4	40.9	28.2	4.2	26.9	26.9	12	13.13	53.51

Table 3.

Nº	Results	children	Adults
1	noun	79.5 ta	67.3 ta
2	A lexeme with a noun	59.1t a	46.4 ta
3	Verb	33.9 ta	40.9 ta
4	Verb lexeme	22.5 ta	28.2 ta
5	Auxiliary verbs	3.5 ta	4.4 ta
6	Conjugated verbs	23.8 ta	26.9 ta
7	Sentence	58 ta	26.9 ta
8	Unfinished sentences (%)	11.3 %	12 %
9	Sentence length	6.15 morf/gap	13.13 morf/gap
10	Speech rate	27.82 so'z/min	53.51 so'z/min

Research discussion. As a result of the research, it was found that in the speech of 4-6-year-old children, nouns are used more often than verbs. Children use more nouns than adults. This was because young children spoke more in counting tones and counted the objects in the pictures when they were shown colorful pictures.

1. Soup, pasta, plov, something else.
2. In the pictures, a teddy bear, a ball, a bus, and the sun are smiling.

In adults, nouns make up 33% of speech. 40% in small ones. He uses nouns in almost half of his speech. Verbs make up 17% of children's speech and 20% of adults' speech. The main difference is the speed of speech and the average value of sentence length. The sentence

length in children averaged 6.15 morphs/sentence and in adults 13.13 morphs/sentence. The reason for this is that children use simple sentences in their speech, while adults use compound sentences.

An example from children's speech:

1. I have broken toys. It is broken and broken. I didn't like them. I'm going to the village.

The gel is intact. My leg is intact.

2. I will bring the spoons. I help look after my brother.

An example from an adult speech:

1. Speaking about the master's degree, the master's degree is the same term for those who will do scientific work in their later life.

2. When I say close to reality, if I can get something for myself from that movie, I like to watch that movie.

In addition, when we observed children's speech, in the picture depicting the zoo, the child said the name of the animal in English because he rarely heard the name of the crocodile in Uzbek, mainly because he heard the word "crocodile" when he saw the crocodile through the English language videos. When the same picture was shown to another child, he called it a "crocodile". Ask this kid, "Which cartoon do you like?" answered "wolf and seven goats". It is known that the child watches more cartoons.

We observed that whether a child goes to kindergarten or not does not affect his speech speed. Participant A1 goes to kindergarten, his speech rate is 31 words per minute, and participant A3 does not go to kindergarten, his speech rate is 35 words per minute.

Conclusion. In this study, we considered questions such as whether the use of nouns and verbs is different in the speech of 4-6-year-old Uzbek children, how the ratio of nouns and verbs in children's speech differs from that of adults. First of all, we studied the studies in other languages (English, French, Chintang, Turkish) that were studied in similar and dissimilar paradigms, and reviewed them through the comparative method. In our research, we also learned that the speed of speech differs between nouns and verbs in the speech of children and adults.

We summarized all the results in a general table and found out that the use of nouns in the speech of children aged 4-6 years is 2 times more than verbs. The average number of nouns used in our study was 79.5. In this case, we can see that children between 4-6 years of age learn more names from the environment and express their thoughts using nouns.

The average use of verbs in children's speech was 33.9. As you can see from the result, the use of verbs is very different from that of nouns. This shows that the acquisition of verbs in children's speech in Uzbek language is low compared to nouns. In comparison with adults, nouns showed an average of 67.3 and verbs an average of 40.9. In the speech of adults, verbs are significantly more than in the speech of children, and nouns are used relatively less.

Through the above indicators, we can see that 4-6-year-old Uzbek children learn and use names more in their speech.

In the next part, the average number of sentences in children's speech was 58, the speed of speech was 27.82, the length of sentences was 6.15, and the number of sentences in adults was 26.9, the speed of speech was 53.51, the length of sentences was 13.13.

In the course of the research, we can conclude that the number of sentences and the length of sentences in children's speech are significantly different from those of adults, that adults use a

lot of auxiliary verbs and sentence expanders, while children use simple sentences and sentences with initial clauses a lot.

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